

Vital Pulp Therapy

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Abstract

One of the most contentious dental topics is vital pulp therapy for cariously exposed permanent teeth. Following pulp exposure, it is preferable to preserve the vitality and health of the exposed pulp rather than replacing it with a root-filling material. Vital pulp therapy (VPT) is important for preserving and maintaining healthy pulp tissue. Recent advancements in pathobiology, bioactive materials, and clinical studies have improved VPT. The current review summarises the clinical outcomes and prognostic factors of VPT in mature permanent teeth with carious pulp exposure, including direct pulp capping, partial pulpotomy, and full pulpotomy, and briefly introduces new progress in this field.

Materials and Methods- An electronic search of the following databases- Pubmed, JOE, Scopus

Introduction

[12] Due to its constantly high success rates, RCT has been viewed as the most effective action for permanent teeth with³ pulpal exposure but a canal with filling materials is biologically substandard to the natural coronal or radicular pulp because they lack the biological immune defense mechanisms and neural innervation.⁴ The prognosis of an endodontically treated teeth is inferior than that of vital teeth. As a result,⁵ procedures preserving the natural tooth with the best available material should be considered.⁶ Vital pulp therapy is used to make teeth symptomless and preserve their strength and functionality. The aim of vital pulp therapy is to protect and sustain the health of the pulp in teeth that have been affected by trauma, decay, restorative treatments, or anatomical irregularities.

The extent of injury to the pulp depends on the treatment modality like for minimal injury a more conventional approach like the Vital Pulp therapy should be approached while in cases of severe injuries a with irreversible pulpitis or Pulp necrosis a Root Canal Treatment should be performed.⁶

Dentistry has recognized the ability of the injured pulp to repair since Philipp Pfaff's first description of direct pulp capping using gold foil in 1756.⁷ Superior sealing properties are now provided by new materials to protect the pulp from microorganisms and

their toxic byproducts. The incorporation of MTA and other hydraulic calcium silicate cements along with new treatment approaches, has challenged the traditional view that VPT should be avoided following carious exposure.⁸

Vital pulp therapy (VPT) is one such method of preserving the vitality of the pulp as well as removing the carious exposure. It includes -

Diagnostic Criteria For VPT

Before proceeding for a VPT a correct diagnosis should be made. The diagnostic criteria mainly includes patients pain history and a proper clinical evaluation by pulp sensibility tests (cold testing and electrical pulp testing) to check the pulp vitality; Mechanical tests like tenderness on percussion; intra-oral radiographs¹¹.

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Dental pulp pain is transmitted through two distinct nerve pathways. Myelinated A-delta ($A\delta$) fibers facilitate rapid pain conduction, producing a piercing, localized, and fast response. When a thermal stimulus is applied to the tooth, it triggers a rapid $A\delta$ fiber response, which subsides almost instantly. In contrast, unmyelinated C-fibers are accountable for slower pain conduction, which is more difficult to localize and primarily induced by heat stimuli. The pain response is initially brief but can become more intense and frequent over time before gradually subsiding. The A fibers are mainly used in the diagnostic criteria.

Indication for Vital Pulp Therapy

⁹VPT is advised for teeth with reversible pulpitis or partly inflamed pulps where the remaining pulp can be preserved to produce a strong barrier that prevents the pulp from future microbial insults. The following methods can be used for the evaluation of teeth for Vital Pulp Therapy-1

Types of Vital Pulp Therapy

1. Indirect Pulp Capping

“A procedure in which a pulp capping material is placed on a thin partition of the remaining carious dentin that, if removed, might expose the pulp in permanent teeth”¹¹ There are two approaches for indirect pulp capping- Two-stage and One stage approach

Two-Stage Approach

All the infected dentin is excavated from the tooth, leaving a layer of the deep carious dentin on the floor as its removal may cause exposure of the pulp.¹¹ Usually, this layer is covered by a liner followed by a temporary/provisional restoration. A follow up After few months the patient revisits where the temporary restoration is removed followed by removal of residual caries and placement of final restorative material.

One Stage Approach

¹¹With a one-stage approach, all/most of the carious structure (usually the infected dentin) is removed leaving behind the affected dentin (demineralised dentin with an intact collagen structure and the ability to undergo remineralisation) during the initial appointment followed by placement of an indirect pulp capping agent near but not directly in contact with the pulp; followed by placement of the final restoration. All the treatment is done in the same appointment. Various dyes and caries detecting solutions can and should be used for differentiating between the carious and sound tooth structure.¹²

1. Direct Pulp Capping

¹²Direct pulp capping is stated as “placing a dental material directly on a mechanical or traumatic vital pulp exposure” and “sealing the pulpal wound to facilitate the formation of reparative dentin and maintenance of the healthy pulp. The most common material used for the direct pulp capping procedure is ¹³Calcium Hydroxide as it has the potential to dissociate into its ionic form, its alkaline pH, bacteriostatic and bactericidal properties and to stimulate the pulp and dentin forming cells in different ways to form reparative dentin.

Ruiz-González et al. analyzed the outcomes of direct pulp capping (DPC) with Irreversible pulpitis. Three studies were studied in a meta analysis involving⁶² teeth showed a joint success rate of 95.3%, including all tested biomaterials achieving success rates above 80%. While the findings support DPC as a potential treatment option, limitations such as small sample sizes and methodological weaknesses underscore the need for more robust researchⁱⁱⁱ

Priya et al. examined the efficacy of laser-assisted direct pulp capping (DPC) in permanent teeth. Their meta-analysis, which included seven studies, indicated that laser treatment significantly reduced both clinical and radiographic failure rates compared to conventional non-laser techniques. This improvement is likely attributed to enhanced decontamination and bio-stimulation. However, variations in study methodologies limit the generalizability of these findings.^{iv}

Pulpotomy

“The removal of the coronal portion of the vital pulp as a means of preserving the vitality of the remaining radicular portion”¹⁴ The process of pulpotomy can be of two types-

Partial Pulpotomy- Partial pulpotomy involves the excavation of a minor section (1-2mm) of the vital pulp to help preserve the remaining pulp tissues.

Steps For Partial Pulpotomy

¹⁶Local anaesthesia and rubber dam application is done to avoid any contamination. The affected area is cleaned by NaOCL or CHX. ¹⁶Caries excavation is done using a high speed #2-6 round burs in a slow-speed handpiece with a hand instrument. The area is irrigated with saline or 1.5% to 5.25% NaOCL to achieve hemostasis by comping the area with a cotton pellet for 5 minutes. ¹⁶In cases of no bleeding, the area is assessed for any necrotic tissue. Uncontrolled bleeding for more than 10 min

should be managed by doing full pulpotomy pulpectomy.¹⁶ Using the appropriate instrument the affected area is sealed with a liner followed by

Lin et al. assessed the clinical and roentographic results of partial pulpotomy and full pulpotomy (FP) in the adult posterior teeth with infected pulpal exposure. The success rates for FP ranged from 92.2% to 99.4%, while Partial pulpotomy showed good success rates between 78.2% and 80.6%. The review found that the choice of material did not significantly influence FP outcomes but had a notable impact on PP success. Although both techniques exhibited high success rates, the study emphasized the need for further long-term research to confirm these findings^v.

Madhumita et al. evaluated the effectiveness of partial pulpotomy (PP) as a conservative approach for managing pulpal involvement in traumatized permanent anterior teeth. Their analysis revealed 89% success, with no evidence of conflict of interest in the study. The review determined that Partial Pulpotomy is a dependable treatment option for symptomless injured permanent single rooted teeth, yielding superior results compared to full pulpotomy (FP)^{vi}

Matoug-Elwerfelli et al. reviewed 14 studies on the effectiveness of Vital Pulp Therapy on teeth with Ellis fractures with or without pulpal. Partial pulpotomy (PP) showed the highest success rates (82.9%–100%), while full pulpotomy (FP) and direct pulp capping (DPC) had less success rates. Bioceramic materials like MTA, Biodentine, iRoot BP and Calcium Hydroxide demonstrated success rates between 79.4% and 100%. The study emphasized the necessity for more rigorous clinical research to validate these findings^{vii}

Donnelly et al. evaluated the pulpotomy success in managing complicated fractured permanent single rooted teeth. The review study reported good results for both partial and full pulpotomy (FP) (70%–98%) but highlighted limitations due to less sample sizes and medium risk of bias. The review recommended Partial Pulpotomy over Pulp Capping in such cases but cautioned that the results should be inferred carefully due to variability among included studies^{viii}

Full Pulpotomy- It is described as the removal of the portion of the vital pulp in the coronal part of the tooth while preserving the vitality of the remaining pulp tissue. This treatment can also be performed as an intervention for symptomatic relief or as a therapeutic approach, such as in Cvek pulpotomy.

Materials used

The ideal material should be biocompatible, possess antibacterial properties, offer strength, create a secure barrier over the pulp wound, stimulate hard tissue formation, and support tissue regeneration^{ix}. Historically various materials were used in vital pulp therapy

¹⁷Calcium Hydroxide - ¹⁸In 1920, calcium hydroxide was presented as a pulp capping agent in endodontics. Calcium hydroxide has long been regarded as the "gold standard" in vital pulp therapy.⁹

Antibacterial action- This feature is due to the release of highly reactive hydroxyl ions, the mode of action of which can be considered to be due to the following mechanisms: bacterial cytoplasmic membrane destruction; protein lysis, and bacterial DNA damage¹⁹. It is effective against the majority of endodontic pathogens.²⁰

Mineralisation Property - This characteristic is caused by the hydroxyl ions, which cause an alkaline pH. The high pH of 10-13 initially causes necrosis on the pulp's surface (1.5-2mm). The toxicity of calcium hydroxide is neutralised in deeper portions of the pulp, resulting in the formation of a layer of tissue that undergoes necrosis at the synapse of necrotic and living pulpal tissue. Calcium hydroxide starts acting as a mild irritant after some point hence, stimulating the formation of hard tissue.²¹ Osteodentine is defined as the calcified material because it has qualities of both bone and dentin.²² CH and MTA may assist in hard tissue growth by disintegrating dentinal growth factors, resulting in the adhesion of pulpal stem cells.

Demerits- The osteodentine barrier formed is often incomplete, thus, forming tunnel defects.²³ Such defects allow bacterial re-infection, reducing the efficiency of the procedure.

²⁴The sterile pulp may get infected due to marginal leakage/ faulty restoration which can further lead to pulpal necrosis if left undiagnosed.

Mineral Trioxide Aggregate

Mineral Trioxide Aggregate (MTA) was introduced for procedures such as Vital Pulp Therapy by Torabinejad and colleagues in the mid-1990s. It has been found to promote mineralization beneath exposed pulp and help preserve pulp vitality. This cement is composed of a hydraulic calcium silicate powder that includes oxide compounds such as calcium oxide, ferric oxide, silicon oxide, sodium and potassium oxides, magnesium oxide, and aluminum oxide.

MTA has beneficial properties supporting reparative dentin formation by stimulating hard tissue-forming cells, encouraging matrix production, and facilitating mineralization. The extracellular matrix contains soluble cytokines and growth factors that play a role in the repair of the dentin-pulp complex. MTA aids in the formation of hard tissue by capturing the growth factors and cytokines within the adjacent dentin matrix. As it sets, MTA gradually releases calcium ions, which contribute to the development of a barrier by activating signaling molecules such as vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), macrophage colony-stimulating factor (MCSF), transforming growth factor (TGF), and interleukins like IL-1. The release of calcium ions from MTA induces an inflammatory response, creating an alkaline environment that leads to tissue necrosis.

Biodentin

BD comes in a capsule containing a powdered blend of tricalcium silicate, dicalcium silicate, zirconium oxide, calcium carbonate, calcium oxide, and iron oxide. Each 0.7 g capsule is mixed for half a minute with a device operating at 4000-4200 rpm with precisely 5 drops of liquid. This liquid includes calcium chloride, which acts as a setting accelerator, a water-soluble polymer that reduces water content. The accelerator enhances handling, improves mechanical strength thus reducing the risk of material loss and interface variation as compared to MTA. However, a notable drawback of BD is its that it has a lower radiopacity than MTA, even after the inclusion of zirconium oxide. Additionally, its radiopacity diminishes over time, making long-term radiographic assessment challenging.

In both direct and indirect pulp capping procedures, BD interacts with hard and soft tissues, ensuring marginal sealing and protecting the preserved vitality by stimulating reactionary dentin formation and remineralization. The release of ions like calcium (Ca^{2+}) and hydroxyl group (OH^-) suggests that tricalcium silicate-based materials like BD may be preferable for indirect pulp capping.

BD achieves marginal sealing through micromechanical retention, as it penetrates tubular structure of dentin and forms tags, providing bond strength to dentin comparable to MTA. However, research findings on its sealing ability are inconsistent, with some studies indicating that BD outperforms MTA in this aspect.

Permanent Restoration

⁶During the next appointment, the tooth is restored with a permanent restoration. ⁶The location of the permanent restoration can be critical to the prolonged preservation of pulp vitality, even more so than the actual pulp treatment. The pulp has the highest chance of repairing if the microleakage is minimal or eliminated. ¹¹The final restorative material is specific for each patient and should be chosen carefully. ⁹Although amalgam has proven to be a reliable material due to its low cost and ease of placement, it does have drawbacks such as aesthetic concerns and potential health risks for dental providers and due to technology advancements and the drawbacks of amalgam it is being replaced by the more advanced adhesive restorative materia

Post Operative Follow Up-

⁹¹¹A post-operative follow-up is always appreciated to assess the treatment outcome. A study defined the sufficient time period for a tentative diagnosis of pulp survivability as 3 months where direct pulp capping was completed with Calcium Hydroxide. ⁹¹¹A two-visit protocol is also helpful in diagnosing the condition of the tooth. Usually, the second visit is after 5-10 days, followed by consecutive visits by 6 weeks, 6 months, and 12 months. The recent advancement of technology in bioactive materials that consistently promote pulp repair and healing has made a progressive and significant contribution to our understanding and ability to protect and maintain living pulp.

Conclusion

Vital pulp therapy (VPT) encompasses various conservative treatments aimed at conserving pulp vitality in teeth, regardless of their stage of development. Techniques such as stepwise removal of caries, IPC, DPC and Pulpotomy, have shown promising success rates depending on clinical indications and pulp status. The introduction of bioceramic materials like MTA, CEM cement and Biodentine™ has notably enhanced treatment outcomes, improving its efficacy and prolonged survival. Neverthe-

less, variations in protocols and the necessity for well-designed, long-term studies remain challenges. Even after these limitations, VPT remains a viable alternative to more invasive procedures like complete pulpectomy, root canal treatment, or tooth extraction. Further research is necessary for ideal protocols and optimized methods for improved success. Further research is required to assess the long-term success of VPT, standardize treatment protocols, and establish objective diagnostic criteria for evaluating pulpal health. Existing evidence indicates that VPT can be effectively performed in both primary and mature permanent teeth with reversible or irreversible pulpitis, provided strict aseptic protocols are followed. These include the use of a dental dam, complete caries removal, confirmation of pulpal vitality through hemostasis and direct visual inspection under magnification, application of biocompatible calcium silicate-based cements (CSCs), and immediate placement of high-quality restorations^{vi}

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